

Use of *N*-Cycloimmonium Salts for the Synthesis of Annelated Heterophospholes

R K BANSAL*, RUCHI MAHNOT, GARIMA PANDEY and RAKHI GUPTA
Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 18 November 1993

Annelated heterophospholes constitute a special class of condensed heterocyclic compounds in which heterophosphole ring is fused with another ring. Heterophospholes are 6π -aromatic systems containing a dicoordinated trivalent (σ^2 , λ^3) phosphorus as one of the members of the five-membered ring. These heterocycles may be considered as derived from typical five-membered aromatic heterocycles, like pyrrole, furan or thiophene by substituting a =CH moiety by an sp^2 -phosphorus (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Similarly, five-membered heterocyclic compounds containing two or more heteroatoms can give rise to a variety of heterophospholes, many of which have already been synthesised and well investigated^{1,2}.

As the heterocyclic compounds containing a five-membered heterocycle (with no phosphorus) annelated to other rings, like benzene, pyridine etc. are well-known and chemically investigated, attempts have been made to obtain the analogous annelated heterophospholes and during the last 10–12 years a variety of such heterocyclic systems have been synthesised.

Different synthetic methodologies have been developed for constructing a heterophosphole

ring^{1,2}, of these one based on 4+1 atom fragment approach³ involving [4+1]cyclocondensation of a four-membered chain with a suitable phosphorus reagent appears to be quite versatile and facile. Various starting materials having CCCC^{4,5}, CNCC^{6,7}, NCNC⁸, NCCN^{9–13}, NCCO¹⁴, NCCS^{14,15}, SCCS¹⁶, NCCP^{17,18} and OCCP¹⁹ chains with sufficiently activated terminal groups have been used for the synthesis of annelated heterophospholes. Both types of phosphorus reagent, electrophilic, e.g. PCl₃, P(NR₂)₃, P(OPh)₃, as well as nucleophilic, e.g. P(SiMe₃)₃, KPH₂ and phosphines have been employed for furnishing phosphorus atom.

N-Cycloimmonium salts having a substituent group in the α -position of the cyclic nitrogen (4) incorporate a four-membered chain which

can condense with an appropriate phosphorus reagent to form an annelated heterophosphole ring. During the last 5–6 years, we have used a variety of such *N*-cycloimmonium salts for the generation of a variety of annelated heterophospholes.

In another methodology, *N*-pyridinium and related salts are first converted into the corresponding *N*-cycloimmonium ylides in the basic

medium which then undergo [3 + 2]-cycloaddition with phosphalkynes or their precursor, phosphalkenes to furnish the annelated heterophospholes. The pyrilium salts undergo O/N exchange with amines to afford pyridines²⁰. This method has been extended to O/P exchange to obtain annelated heterophospholes from the oxazolo-pyridinium and related salts.

The present review deals with the use of various *N*-cycloimmonium salts for the synthesis of annelated heterophospholes through different routes. The emphasis is placed on the nature of the starting *N*-cycloimmonium salts and not the products. The reactions of the heterophospholes will not be described here. The literature has been covered upto August, 1993.

Use of *N*-pyridinium and related salts

N-Pyridinium and related salts have been converted into the corresponding annelated heterophospholes through three methods : (i) [4 + 1]-cyclocondensation, (ii) [3 + 2]-cycloaddition and (iii) O/P exchange.

[4 + 1]-Cyclocondensation :

This synthetic procedure involves cyclocondensation of a dialkyl-, alkylamino- or diamino-pyridinium salt with an appropriate phosphorus reagent in the presence of a base. Usually PCl_3 or $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$ have been used for this purpose. The former requires the use of a base, which is generally Et_3N , but in the latter case no extra base is necessary as the liberated dimethylamine acts as a base for further reaction.

1,2-Dialkylpyridinium bromides : 1,2-Dialkylpyridinium bromides condense with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to afford 2-phosphaindolizines or 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (**6**) (Scheme 2)^{6,7}.

Sufficient activation of *N*-methylene group is a prerequisite for the above condensation, in the absence of which the reaction may stop at the intermediate state. In case of **5** ($\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{COOEt}$, $\text{R}^3 = \text{R}^4 = \text{H}$), an intermediate

Scheme 2

pyridinium ylide (**7**) could be isolated which cyclised on prolonged heating⁶. But the reaction of **5** ($\text{R}^1 = \text{R}^3 = \text{R}^4 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{Ph}$) formed **8** which did not cyclise even on heating²¹.

The condensation of 2-methylpyridinium bromides (**5**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$) with PCl_3 sometimes leads to the formation of 1-dichlorophosphino derivative (**10**) alongwith 1-unsubstituted-2-phosphaindolizine (**9**). It has been independently shown that **10** results from the electrophilic substitution of the initially formed 1-unsubstituted-2-phosphaindolizine with PCl_3 (Scheme 3)²².

Scheme 3

The preparation of 2-phosphaindolizines by the above method parallels the synthesis of indolizines from cyclocondensation of the pyridinium salts with acid anhydrides²³.

The 2-phosphaindolizines (**6** and **9**) are mostly pale yellow to brown crystalline solids, but in some cases oily products. These are stable under nitrogen for prolonged periods of time, but rapidly hydrolyse in moist air. These compounds show characteristically downfield ³¹P nmr chemical shift in the range δ 132–184.

1,2-Dialkyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinolinium bromide : 1-Phenacyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinolinium bromide (**11**) also condenses with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to give a tricyclic phosphaindolizine (**12**)⁶.

1-Alkyl-2-aminopyridinium salts : 1-Alkyl-2-aminopyridinium bromides obtained from alkylation of 2-aminopyridines condense with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to give 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines, i.e. 1,4,2-diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]pyridines (**14**)⁸.

In contrast to 1,2-dialkylpyridinium bromides, the reaction is initiated in the above case on 2-amino group of the pyridinium salt as proved by the isolation of the intermediate, (1-alkyl-1,2-dihydro-2-pyridinylideneamino)dichlorophosphine (**15**). The latter on treating with additional amount of triethylamine changes into **14**⁸.

1,3,4-Diazaphospholopyridines (**14**) are pale yellow crystalline solids which are rapidly hydrolysed by water. These compounds show a low field ^{31}P nmr chemical shift in the range δ 233–238.

2-Alkyl-1-aminopyridinium iodides : 2-Alkylpyridines on *N*-amination with hydroxylamine-*o*-sulphonic acid in presence of hydriodic acid give 2-alkyl-1-aminopyridinium iodides²⁴ which condense with PCl_3 in the presence of triethylamine to give 3-aza-2-phosphaindolizine, i.e. 1,2,3-diazaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (**18**) (Scheme 4)²⁵.

Scheme 4

1-Unsubstituted-3-aza-2-phosphaindolizine (**18**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$) is sometimes accompanied by 1-dichlorophosphino derivative (**19**), which is formed by subsequent reaction of **18** with PCl_3 ²⁵.

1,2,3-Diazaphospholopyridines (**18**) are colourless to pale yellow solids or syrupy mass which are highly sensitive to moisture. The ^{31}P nmr chemical shifts of these compounds lie in the range δ 235–238.

1,2-Diaminopyridinium iodides : 2-Aminopyridines could also be *N*-aminated²⁶ and the resulting 1,2-diaminopyridinium salts condense with $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$ in refluxing benzene to give 1,2,4,3-triazaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (**21**) (Scheme 5)²⁷.

Scheme 5

The condensation with PCl_3 stopped at the intermediate state (**22**), which did not change into the heterophosphole derivative even on prolonged heating.

The above reaction is expected to proceed through the intermediate formation of 1-amino-2-imino-2H-pyridine, which is proved by an independent synthesis of **24** from **23** ($\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Ph}$)²⁸.

1,2,4,3-Triazaphospholopyridines are white crystalline sublimable solids which are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. In ^{31}P nmr spectra, these compounds absorb further downfield in the range δ 265–268.

[3+2]-Cycloaddition :

N-Cycloimmonium salts generate *N*-ylides in the basic medium which can act as 1,3-dipoles and hence undergo [3 + 2]-cycloadditions with unsaturated compounds^{29,30}. Phosphaalkynes (**25**) and their precursor, phosphaalkenes (**26**) have been found to undergo [3 + 2]-cycloadditions with a variety of 1,3-dipoles to give different heterophospholes^{31,32}. In some cases, regioselectivity is observed.

Recently, this methodology has been used for the synthesis of a few annelated heterophospholes.

N-Pyridinium salts : The *N*-pyridinium ylide (**27**) generated from the corresponding salt undergoes [3 + 2]-cycloaddition with the phosphaalkynes (**28**) to form 2-phosphaindolizines (**29**) regioselectively. However, in case of the ylide (**30**), a mixture of two stereoisomers (**31** and

Scheme 6

32) is formed. The ratio of the isomers is influenced by the nature of the substituent groups (R^1, R^2) in the pyridinium ring and in case of $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}, \text{R}^2 = \text{O}^i\text{Pr}$, only **31** is formed (Scheme 7)³³.

Scheme 7

N-Isoquinolinium salts : The *N*-isoquinolinium ylide (**33**) reacts similarly with the phosphaalkynes (**25**) to form the annelated 1,3-azaphosphole (**34**) regioselectively, although the dipole orientation is reversed³³ (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

O/P-Exchange :

The pyrilium salts on reacting with tris(trimethylsilyl)phosphine, $P(\text{SiMe}_3)_3$, undergo *O/P* exchange to form λ^3 -phosphinines³⁴. This synthetic strategy has been extended to the annelated pyridinium salts.

The [1,3]-oxazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium (35) and [1,3,4]-oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium salts (37) react with $P(\text{SiMe}_3)_3$ to give 1-phosphaindolizine (36) and 3-aza-1-phosphaindolizine (38) respectively (Scheme 9)³⁵.

Scheme 9

[1,3]-Oxazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium-2-olate under similar conditions gives 2-hydroxy-1-phosphaindolizine (36; $R = \text{OH}$) which shows phenolic character and could be acylated³⁶.

1-Phosphaindolizines are low melting solids or yellow oils. In contrast to 2-phosphaindolizines, these compounds absorb in ^{31}P nmr in the upfield region (δ 54–76), which may be attributed to the contribution by the mesomeric structure (39).

Use of diazinium and related salts

Some diazinium salts have been used for the preparation of the corresponding annelated heterophospholes.

[4+1]-Cyclocondensation :

1,2-Dialkylpyrazinium bromide : 2,5-Dimethyl-1-phenacylpyrazinium bromide (40) condenses with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to afford 3-benzoyl-6-methyl-7-aza-2-phosphaindolizine (41) in low yield⁶.

Although corresponding reactions of the pyridazinium and pyrimidinium salts have not been investigated so far, 42 did not give the expected product 43 on reacting with PCl_3 and Et_3N ³⁷.

[3 + 2]-Cycloadditions :

N-Pyridazinium salt : The *N*-pyridazinium dicyanomethylide (44) undergoes [3 + 2]-cycloaddition with the phosphalkyne (28) to give a 1 : 1 mixture of 5-aza-2-phosphaindolizine (45) and 5-aza-1-phosphaindolizine (46)³³ (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

N-Pyrazinium salts : Similarly, *N*-pyrazinium ylide (47) reacts with 28 to form a 1 : 1 mixture of two isomeric azaphosphaindolizines (48 and 49) (Scheme 11)³³.

Scheme 11

N-Phthalazinium salts : The methodology involving [3 + 2]-cycloaddition of *N*-cycloimmonium ylide with the phosphalkyne has been successfully employed to the synthesis of 1,3-azaphospholo[2,1-*a*]phthalazine (**51**)³³ (Scheme 12). The structure of the product has been confirmed by X-ray crystal studies.

Scheme 12

2,3-Dialkyl-4,5-dihydrooxazolium salts

2-Ethyl-3-phenacyl-4,5-dihydrooxazolium bromide (**52**) condenses with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to give 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*b*]-5,

6-dihydrooxazole (**53**)³⁸. In this connection, it is found that the 4,5-dihydrooxazolium salts with less activated *N*-methylene group (**52**; $\text{R} = \text{Ph}$, CO_2R) do not undergo [4 + 1]-cyclocondensation and the reaction stops at the stage of the intermediate, *N*-(dichlorophosphinylmethylene)-4,5-dihydrooxazolium ylide (cf. 7).

N-Thiazolium and related salts

N-Thiazolium-4,5-dihydrothiazolium and -benzothiazolium salts have also been used for obtaining different annelated heterophospholes.

2,3-Dialkylthiazolium salts :

2,3-Dialkyl-4,5-dihydrothiazolium bromides (**54**) and 2,3-dialkylbenzothiazolium bromides (**56**) condense with PCl_3 in the presence of Et_3N to give the respective annelated heterophospholes³⁹ (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Although 1-unsubstituted derivatives of **55** ($\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$) and **57** ($\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$) could not be obtained, their dichlorophosphinylated products (**55**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{PCl}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{COOEt}$ and **57**; $\text{R}^1 = \text{PCl}_2$, $\text{R}^2 = \text{COOEt}$) have been obtained from the reaction of the respective *N*-cycloimmonium bromides with two equivalents of PCl_3 .

In the case of 2-ethyl-3-alkylbenzothiazolium bromides, the intermediate (*N*-dichlorophosphinylmethylene)immonium ylide (**58**) ($\delta^{31}\text{P}$, 177–186) could be isolated and characterised.

The ylidic nature of **58c** is confirmed by its behaviour towards aluminium trichloride when *C*-benzothiazolo-*p*-chlorophosphaalkene tetrachloroaluminate (**59**) ($\delta^{31}\text{P}$, 268) is formed³⁹.

Azaphospholothiazoles (**55**) and -benzothiazoles (**57**) are coloured solids, in some cases syrupy

mass. These compounds show a characteristically downfield ^{31}P nmr chemical shift (δ 130–203).

3-Alkyl-2-aminothiazolium- and related salts :

Like 1-alkyl-2-aminopyridinium salts, 3-alkyl-2-aminothiazolium bromide (**60**), its 4,5-dihydro derivative (**62**) and benzo derivatives (**64**) also condense with PCl_3 and triethylamine to form the corresponding annelated heterophospholes (Scheme 14)⁴⁰. These products are colourless solids, highly sensitive to moisture, rapidly hydrolysing in the atmosphere but can be stored under dry nitrogen for prolonged periods of time. A downfield ^{31}P nmr shift (δ 252–269) is characteristic of these compounds.

As in the case of 1-alkyl-2-aminopyridinium bromides, the reaction of 3-alkyl-2-aminothiazolium and related salts with PCl_3 is initiated by the attack of the latter on 2-amino group which is proved by the isolation of the intermediate,

Scheme 14

thiazol-2-ylidenaminodichlorophosphines **66** and **67** (δ ^{31}P , 150–162) under mild conditions. The latter could be converted into the azaphospholo derivatives by additional amount of triethylamine (Scheme 15)⁴¹.

Scheme 15

2,3-Diaminothiazolium salts :

Recently, [1,3]thiazolo[2,3-*e*][1,2,4,3]triazaphosphole derivative (**69**) has been obtained⁴² from the condensation of 2,3-diamino-4-methylthiazolium chloride (**68**)⁴³ with PCl_3 or $\text{P}(\text{NMe}_2)_3$.

Concluding remarks :

In the present brief review, an attempt has been made to highlight the utility of well-known and easily obtainable *N*-cycloimmonium salts for the synthesis of new classes of heterocyclic systems. The reactions are easily manipulated and the synthesised products show interesting reactivities being explored by our research group.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to the Department of Atomic Energy Commission for Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (G.P.)

and to Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, for Junior Research Fellowship to the other (R.G.) as financial support.

References

1. A. SCHMIDPETER and K. KARAGHIOFF in "Rings, Clusters and Polymers of Main Group and Transition Elements", ed. H. W. ROESKY, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1989, p. 307.
2. A. SCHMIDPETER and K. KARAGHIOFF in "Multiple Bonds and Low Coordination in Phosphorus Chemistry", eds. M. REGITZ and O. J. SCHERER, Thieme, Stuttgart, 1990, p. 258.
3. C. W. BIRD and G. W. H. CHEESEMAN, 'Synthesis of Five-membered Rings with one Heteroatom' in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", eds. A. R. KATRITZKY and C. W. REES, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 4, p. 115.
4. A. SCHMIDPETER and M. THIELE, *Angew. Chem.*, 1991, **103**, 333.
5. C. L. LIOTTA, M. L. MCHANGHLIN, D. G. DERVEER and B. A. O'BRIEN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 1665.
6. R. K. BANSAL, K. KARAGHIOFF, N. GUPTA, A. SCHMIDPETER and C. SPINDLER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1991, **124**, 475.
7. R. K. BANSAL, V. KABRA, N. GUPTA and K. KARAGHIOFF, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 254.
8. K. KARAGHIOFF, R. K. BANSAL and N. GUPTA, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1992, **47**, 373.
9. K. KARAGHIOFF, W. S. SHELDRIK and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1986, **119**, 3213.
10. T. A. KHWAJA and H. PANDE, *Nucleic Acid Res.*, 1979, 251.
11. J. P. MAJORAL, R. KRAEMER, T. N'GANDO M'PONDO and J. NAVECH, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, **21**, 1307.
12. K. KARAGHIOFF, J. P. MAJORAL, A. MERIEM, J. NAVECH and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 2137.
13. C. MALAUAUD, M. T. BOISDON, Y. CHARBONNEL and J. BARRANS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, 447.
14. C. MALAUAUD, L. LOPEZ, T. N'GANDO M'PONDO, M. T. BOISDON, Y. CHARBONNEL and J. BARRANS, *A. C. S. Symp. Ser.*, 1981, **171**, 415.
15. N. BURFORD, A. I. DIPCHAND, B. W. ROYAN and P. W. WHITE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 4938.
16. N. BURFORD, B. W. ROYAN, A. LINDIN and T. S. CAMERON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 144.
17. K. ISSLEIB, R. VOLLMER, H. OEHME and H. MEYER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 441.
18. J. HEINICKE and A. TZSCHACH, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **23**, 3643.
19. K. ISSLEIB and R. VOLLMER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, **21**, 3483.
20. A. R. KATRITZKY, *Tetrahedron*, 1980, **36**, 679.
21. R. K. BANSAL, R. GUPTA and G. PANDEY, Unpublished results.
22. R. K. BANSAL, N. GUPTA, V. KABRA, C. SPINDLER, K. KARAGHIOFF and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Heteroatom Chem.*, 1992, **3**, 359.
23. F. W. KROECK and F. KROEHNKE, *Chem. Ber.*, 1969, **102**, 669.
24. R. GOESL and A. MEUWSEN, *Org. Synth.*, 1963, **43**, 1.
25. R. K. BANSAL, G. PANDEY and R. GUPTA, Unpublished results.
26. K. T. POTTS, H. R. BURTON and J. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 260.
27. R. K. BANSAL and N. GANDHI, Unpublished results.
28. A. SCHMIDPETER, F. STEINMULLER and E. YA. ZABOTINA, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1993, **335**, 458.
29. I. ZUGRAVESCU and M. PETROVANU, "N-Ylid Chemistry", Eng. Translation by C. STOICESCU, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1976
30. Review : R. HUISGEN, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1963, **2**, 565.
31. Review : M. REGITZ, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 191.
32. Review : M. REGITZ and P. BINGER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1988, **100**, 1541; *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 1484.
33. U. BERGSTRASSER, A. HOFFMANN and M. REGITZ, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 1049.
34. Review : G. MAERKL in "Multiple Bonds and Low Coordination in Phosphorus Chemistry", eds. M. REGITZ and O. J. SCHERER, Thieme, Stuttgart, 1990, p. 220.
35. G. MAERKL and S. PFLAUM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28**, 1511.
36. G. MAERKL and S. PFLAUM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **29**, 3387.
37. R. K. BANSAL and R. GUPTA, Unpublished results.
38. R. K. BANSAL, C. B. JAIN, N. GUPTA, V. KABRA, K. KARAGHIOFF and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Phosphorus, Sulfur Silicon*, 1994, **86**, 139.
39. R. K. BANSAL, R. MAHNOT, D. C. SHARMA, K. KARAGHIOFF and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Heteroatom Chem.*,

- BANSAL, MAHNOT, PANDEY & GUPTA · USE OF *N*-CYCLOIMMONIUM SALTS FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF ANNELATED *etc.*
1992, **3**, 351.
- 40 R. K. BANSAL, R. MAHNOT, D. C. SHARMA and K
KARAGHIOSOFF, *Synthesis*, 1992, 267.
- 41 R. K. BANSAL, D. C. SHARMA and R. MAHNOT, *Tetrahedron
Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 6433.
42. A. SCHMIDPETER, F. STEINMULLER and E. YA. ZABOTINA,
J. Prakt. Chem., 1993, **335**, 458.
43. H. BEYER, W. LAESSIG and G. RUHLIG, *Chem. Ber.*,
1953, **86**, 764; H. BEYER, W. LAESSIG and E. BULKA,
Chem. Ber., 1954, **87**, 1385.

